

KINETICS OF HYDROGENATION OF OILS IN A CONTINUOUS PROCESS.

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The corrected velocity coefficients (k') have been calculated for the hydrogenation of safflower, sesame, cottonseed and groundnut oils in a continuous process. The values 2 and 4 obtained for the exponent n in the equation.

$$k = k'R \frac{x}{n}$$

have been shown to be due to the activated absorption of olein and linolein respectively. The heats of activation calculated for oils containing different percentages of olein and linolein have shown that the heats of activation are about 2K cal. and 8K cal. for olein and linolein respectively.

Armstrong and Hilditch (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1919, 96A, 137) found that the rate of hydrogenation in a batch process is a linear² function of time. Similar view is held by Richardson and co-workers (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1924, 16, 519). Thomas (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1920, 39, 10T) found that the hydrogenation of olive oil by batch process is of mono-molecular type. Armstrong and Hilditch (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1920, 98A, 27) explained the gradually decreasing rates observed by Thomas to the use of a closed system and the consequent accumulation of gaseous impurities which acted as poisons. Thomas found an increase of 2.8 times in the rate of reaction for a 60° rise in temperature.

Lush (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1924, 44, 129T) from his study of the hydrogenation of cottonseed oil by the continuous method has shown the absorption of hydrogen to be independent of the flow of oil within certain limits. Athavale and Jatkar (*J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1939, 21A, 321) have made a systematic study of the continuous method of hydrogenation and followed the kinetics of reaction by the space-time yields, assuming that the reaction proceeds in a logarithmic manner along the length of the tube; the percentage conversion in one passage over the catalyst represented an integrated reaction over the whole length of the tube. The formulae used for calculating velocity coefficients was of the first order,

$$k = 2.3 R \log \frac{a}{a-x}$$

where R is the rate of the oil flowing over the catalyst and k is the apparent velocity coefficient. They obtained concordant values at all rates,

in the case of nickel wire catalyst at 140°, 160°, and 180°. The nickel carbonate-kieselguhr catalyst gave varying values for the velocity coefficients in the case of hydrogenation of groundnut, cottonseed and olive oils.

The velocity coefficients calculated from the unimolecular formula is only a measure of the association between the unsaturated compound and the catalyst at a particular rate in unit length of the catalyst. From the variation of the values of k , it appeared that the association between the unsaturated compound and the catalyst is influenced by rate. The variation in the values of k can be expressed by

$$k = k' R^{\frac{1}{n}}$$

where k' and n are positive constants.

Athavale and Jatkar (*loc. cit.*) obtained concordant values for k' in the case of hydrogenation of groundnut, cottonseed and olive oils by nickel carbonate-kieselguhr catalysts. n has been shown by them to be a function of temperature. The present work is an extension of the study of the kinetics of hydrogenation of oils in a continuous process with reference to safflower, sesame, cottonseed and groundnut oils.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

The apparatus used was the same as described by Athavale and Jatkar (*loc. cit.*). 20% Nickel carbonate-kieselguhr catalyst was used.

The Velocity Coefficients.

The corrected velocity coefficients for safflower, sesame, cottonseed and groundnut oils, obtained by using the formula $k = k' (r)^{\frac{1}{n}}$ are given in Tables I and II.

TABLE I.

Rate.	Vel. coeff. of safflower oil at					Vel. coeff. of sesame oil at				
	100°	120°	140°	160°	180°	100°	120°	140°	160°	180°
40	1'09	4'19	2'83	7'67	5'37	2'03	0'47	2'62	1'41	8'27
60	1'03	4'00	2'99	7'48	5'71	2'16	0'43	2'85	1'35	8'10
80	1'10	4'30	3'01	7'47	5'56	2'13	0'43	2'88	1'39	8'46
100	1'08	4'26	2'80	7'36	5'56	2'12	(0'33)	(2'46)	1'31	8'35
Mean	1'05	4'19	2'91	7'50	5'55	2'11	0'44	2'78	1'36	8'30
n	2	3'8	2'3	4'4	2	2'6	1	1'8	1'4	3

TABLE II.

Rate.	Vel. coeff. of cottonseed oil at			Vel. coeff. of groundnut oil at		
	140°.	160°.	180°.	100°.	140°.	180°.
40	(1·82)	9·50	13·6	2·97	4·07	6·91
60	2·23	9·27	(14·6)	2·66	4·17	6·77
80	2·28	9·31	13·7	2·63	4·02	6·88
100	2·17	9·51	13·6	2·61	3·88	6·73
Mean	2·22	9·39	13·65	2·72	4·01	6·82
<i>n</i>	2	4	4	2	2	2

For safflower and sesame oils the apparent velocity coefficients k increase steadily with increasing temperature showing a maximum and a minimum near about 140° and 160° respectively. The maxima and minima are more predominant with faster rates which is in accordance with results obtained by Athavale and Jatkar for groundnut oil (*loc. cit.*) who attributed the peaks in the k -temperature curves to the faster velocity of the hydrogenation of linolein.

The study of the selectivity of hydrogenation by the authors (Joglekar and Jatkar, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1941, 23A, 139) has shown that for sesame oil the reaction, olein-stearin proceeds best at 140°. This reaction is less pronounced in the case of safflower oil which has a very high content of linolein.

At 160° for safflower, sesame and cottonseed oils, it has been observed by us (*loc. cit.*) that linolein-stearin reaction takes place exclusively.

The n obtained for groundnut oil is 2 which confirms the value obtained by Athavale and Jatkar. In the case of oils containing higher proportion of linolein ($n=4$) at higher temperatures at which preferential hydrogenation of linolein takes place.

The Apparent Heats of Activation.

The apparent heats of activation E are calculated from the corrected velocity coefficients k' for 20% nickel catalyst at 150°.

TABLE V.

Oil	... Groundnut.	Sesame.	Safflower.	Cottonseed.
E	... 2'1	2'5	7'2	11'1

The lower heat of activation for the hydrogenation of olein than that observed for ethylene and other ethylenic compounds (which is about 10 K cal.) is due to the higher activity of the catalyst. The increased heat of activation for oils containing linolein is obviously accounted for on the basis of increased energy required for activation of two double bonds.

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